

ATOMIC OXYGEN PROTECTION OF MATERIALS FOR SPACE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The low Earth orbit (LEO) space environment can seriously degrade and erode spacecraft surfaces, especially organic materials such as graphite/epoxy, polycarbonates, and polyimides. Atomic oxygen, the major constituent of the LEO atmosphere at Space Shuttle altitudes, is the principal cause of the erosion. For long duration LEO missions, atomic oxygen reactive materials must be protected from the environment. Several protective coating schemes from metal foils to thin film ceramics have been proposed for different spacecraft applications. In this paper, we will summarize our test results for thin film oxides (SiO_2 , Al_2O_3) and nitrides (Si_3N_4) and discuss the work of other researchers in the area of atomic oxygen protective coatings. Our work has shown that when properly deposited, a coating layer of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 or Si_3N_4 of about 750\AA is adequate to completely stop atomic oxygen penetration to the substrate.

KEYWORDS: Atomic Oxygen; Low Earth Orbit; Protective Coatings; Thin Films; Composites

1. INTRODUCTION

As a spacecraft moves in and out of the earth's shadow in low Earth orbit (LEO), its surfaces are bombarded by atomic oxygen and micrometeorites/debris, exposed to ultraviolet (UV) radiation, and temperature cycled. Material degradation such as erosion and changes in surface morphology have been observed in samples retrieved after exposure to the LEO environment, and atomic oxygen is primarily responsible for these effects due to its high oxidative ability, high collision energy (≈ 5 eV for a spacecraft traveling at 8 km/s), and high flux (10^{15} atoms/s-cm²).^{1,2} Results obtained from materials flown on the Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF), which was in LEO for over 5 years, showed that some materials were

severely degraded. For example, a Kapton sheet of 7.6×10^{-3} cm (0.003") which was the top layer of a multilayer insulation blanket was completely eroded. A sample of silverized fluorinated ethylene-propylene (FEP) Teflon, with Teflon as the outer surface and silver coated on the back, showed erosion of 3.3×10^{-3} cm (0.0013") and changes in surface morphology after retrieval from the LDEF. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) photographs of Teflon surfaces flown on the LDEF which were protected from the LEO environment and exposed to the LEO environment are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Organic composites are attractive candidates for spacecraft applications because they offer excellent mechanical properties (high strength to weight ratio, high impact resistance, low coefficient of thermal expansion). Organic materials such as graphite/epoxy, however, are susceptible to atomic oxygen attack.³ SEM photographs of a control graphite/epoxy sample which was not exposed to atomic oxygen and of a graphite/epoxy sample which was exposed to atomic oxygen in an oxygen plasma asher (total estimated fluence of 1.2×10^{21} atoms/cm²) are presented in Figures 3 and 4. The SEM photograph of the atomic oxygen exposed graphite/epoxy sample shows that there was significant erosion of the epoxy matrix as well as of the graphite fibers. If organic composites are to be used on long duration LEO missions, they must be protected from atomic oxygen bombardment. Several types of coatings, from metal foils to thin film ceramic coatings, have been proposed for atomic oxygen reactive substrates. For use on spacecraft hardware, factors such as ease of coating application on a large-scale basis, coating/substrate adhesion, and coating damage tolerance must all be taken into consideration. The use of organic composites on long duration LEO spacecraft, therefore, remains a challenge.

2. PROTECTIVE COATINGS FOR ATOMIC OXYGEN SUSCEPTIBLE SURFACES

One alternative for protecting composites from atomic oxygen in the LEO environment is to wrap the composite substrate with a metal foil.^{4,5} A Boeing study on using anodized aluminum foil as a coating for composite truss tubes found that both phosphoric acid and chromic acid anodized aluminum foils retained their adhesion to the composite tubes and optical properties stability when subjected to atomic oxygen and thermal cycling representative of the LEO environment.⁴ One major concern is the impact damage which can occur from hypervelocity impact from debris or micrometeoroids. If a portion of the foil is removed, the composite is susceptible to atomic oxygen attack and tube failure can result even if the impact event causes no structural damage.⁵

Results from LDEF have shown that a very thin layer of a stable metal, such as aluminum, can provide excellent protection against atomic oxygen attack. McDonnell Douglas had a multilayer insulation blanket consisting of layers of Kapton which was flown on the LDEF. The top layer of Kapton was not coated on the exposed surface and was completely eroded. The underlying layers, however, were coated with 400Å aluminum on both sides. Examination of the underlying layers showed that the 400Å aluminum provided excellent atomic oxygen protection of the Kapton.

Within the space materials community, a variety of candidate coatings have been developed for use in LEO. NASA-Lewis Research Center (LeRC) developed an ion beam sputter-deposited metal oxide-fluoropolymer thin film coating using SiO₂ and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE Teflon).⁶ In these coatings, the SiO₂ provides atomic oxygen protection and the fluoropolymer provides flexibility. The LeRC coatings were evaluated both in laboratory plasma ashing tests and in space on board Shuttle flight STS-8 for effectiveness in preventing the oxidation of polyimide Kapton. Mass loss and optical measurements of the LeRC samples after exposure to atomic oxygen indicated that these coatings were very effective in protecting the polyimide. Canadian researchers have developed protective coatings using microwave glow discharge deposition of volatile compounds to produce amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) and inorganic silicon (P-SiN and P-SiO₂) coatings.⁷ Mass loss and SEM analyses of these coatings showed that they also provided good protection of the substrates against atomic oxygen attack.

As a part of McDonnell Douglas Space System Company's (MDSSC-SSD) independent research and development program, we have investigated oxide and nitride thin films as coatings for atomic oxygen protection. In our atomic oxygen work, we have been collaborating with Los Alamos National Laboratory, principal investigator Dr. Jon B. Cross. Los Alamos National Laboratory has an excellent atomic oxygen simulation facility which can produce a beam of neutral atomic oxygen of hyperthermal (1-5 eV) energy and at accelerated fluxes (1 - 100X LEO conditions).⁸ In our work to date, the coatings we have evaluated for atomic oxygen resistance include silicon dioxide (SiO₂), silicon nitride (Si₃N₄), and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃).

To determine the effectiveness of coatings, we developed an oxygen sensor based on using silver oxidation to detect atomic oxygen penetration through thin films.⁹ Silver oxidizes rapidly in the presence of atomic oxygen, and its electrical resistance increases significantly. The oxygen sensors are made of a sapphire or alumina substrate and have strips of silver (typically 250Å) deposited on them. The

coatings of interest (typically $<1000\text{\AA}$) are then deposited on top of the silver, and the electrical resistance of the silver is measured in-situ during atomic oxygen exposure. If atomic oxygen penetrates the coating, the electrical resistance of the silver increases.

Our test results showed that thin layers of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Si_3N_4 , when deposited properly, can completely block atomic oxygen penetration to the substrate. In our 1990 work, thin films of SiO_2 (771\AA), Al_2O_3 (755\AA), and Si_3N_4 (707\AA) were ion beam sputter-deposited on oxygen sensors, made of very smooth sapphire substrates, and exposed to the atomic oxygen beam at Los Alamos National Laboratory. The electrical resistance of the silver underneath the coating was measured in-situ during exposure. When the oxide and nitride coated oxygen sensors were exposed to the atomic oxygen beam at constant temperature, there was no rise in the electrical resistance of the silver. A plot of the silver electrical resistance vs. atomic oxygen fluence for an Al_2O_3 (755\AA) coated oxygen sensor which was exposed to 2 eV atomic oxygen at 68°C is shown in Figure 5. A plot of the silver electrical resistance vs. atomic oxygen fluence for a SiO_2 (771\AA) coated oxygen sensor which was exposed to 2 eV atomic oxygen at 80°C is shown in Figure 6. Our results indicated that these oxide and nitride thin films are capable of completely blocking atomic oxygen penetration to the underlying substrate.

The performance of these thin films under an atomic oxygen environment, however, is strongly dependent on the quality of the films as well as the preparation of the substrate surface. In our earlier (1988-89) work with Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 films, we sputter deposited them on oxygen sensors made of alumina substrates, which had a much rougher surface texture. The alumina substrates had surface roughnesses on the order of $2\text{-}3\ \mu\text{m}$, whereas the sapphire substrates were much smoother, with surface roughness of $<0.05\ \mu\text{m}$. Our results with Al_2O_3 (950\AA) and SiO_2 (950\AA) films deposited on oxygen sensors with rough alumina substrates indicated that there was steady oxygen penetration through the films to the underlying silver, and the silver electrical resistance eventually increased to megohms.¹⁰ There were also large variations in the fluence lifetimes of coatings, where the fluence lifetime of a coating was defined as the total atomic oxygen fluence which the coating could withstand before the silver electrical resistance reached megohms. The results indicated that there may have been incomplete coating protection of the substrate and that if rough substrate surfaces are to be coated, coatings much thicker than 1000\AA are required.

In 1989, we undertook an in-depth study of atomic oxygen effects on thin film (750\AA) Al_2O_3 .¹¹ These Al_2O_3 films were also ion beam sputter-deposited, but using different parameters than the films we investigated in 1990. When using

even smooth sapphire oxygen sensors, we had found atomic oxygen permeation through the Al_2O_3 coating. Our results indicated that the coatings provided much better protection of the substrate when deposited on smooth sapphire surfaces than when deposited on rough alumina surfaces. It is not the purpose of this paper to evaluate how the atomic oxygen resistance of oxide and nitride thin films vary with deposition parameters, but our results show that the quality of the coatings (e.g. density, porosity, impurities) and the surface condition of the substrate can significantly affect the performance of the coatings.

3. SUMMARY

In summary, the use of organic composites on long duration missions in LEO requires the protection of these surfaces from the space environment. A variety of coatings, from standard coatings currently used in the space material industry to novel coatings under development, are available. There are a number of considerations in the selection of a coating. The ability to manufacture and deposit the coating on a large scale basis, the adhesion of the coating to the substrate, and the damage tolerance of the coating are important considerations. The quality of the coating as well as the substrate surface preparation also affect the performance of a coating. In our work with oxide and nitride thin films, we have shown that thin films ($<1000\text{\AA}$) of stable oxide and nitride materials such as SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Si_3N_4 are capable of preventing penetration of atomic oxygen to the substrate.

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Figure 1: Scanning electron microscope photograph of a FEP Teflon sample (silverized on the back surface) which was protected from the low Earth orbit environment while onboard the Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF). This FEP sample had smooth surfaces and was visibly reflective because of the silver on the back surface.

Figure 2: Scanning electron microscope photograph of a FEP Teflon sample which was exposed to the low Earth orbit environment during the LDEF mission. There was erosion of the Teflon, and the front surface has been considerably roughened. In contrast to the protected FEP Teflon, the exposed FEP sample did not appear reflective but had a "milky" white appearance.

Figure 3: Scanning electron microscope photograph of a control graphite/epoxy composite sample which was not exposed to atomic oxygen. As expected, the graphite fibers are well covered by epoxy.

Figure 4: Scanning electron microscope photograph of a graphite/epoxy sample which was exposed to an estimated atomic oxygen fluence of 1.2×10^{21} atoms/cm². Both the graphite fibers as well as the epoxy matrix have been severely eroded.

Figure 5: This figure shows that aluminum oxide of 755Å was able to completely block atomic oxygen penetration to the silver substrate. There was no increase in the electrical resistance of silver underneath the Al_2O_3 with atomic oxygen exposure.

Figure 6: This figure shows that silicon dioxide of 771Å was also able to completely block atomic oxygen penetration to the silver substrate. There was no increase in the electrical resistance of silver underneath the SiO_2 with atomic oxygen exposure.

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